

Stability against photodegradation of a photochromic spirooxazine dye embedded in amino-functionalized sol-gel hybrid coatings

Rosario Pardo · Marcos Zayat · David Levy

Abstract A photochromic spirooxazine derivative, 1-propyl-3,3,5,6-tetramethyl-spiro[indoline-2-3⁰-[quinolino]oxazine], was successfully embedded in sol-gel thin silica films functionalized with different amino groups. The resulting films show high transparency and exhibit a strong blue coloration upon irradiation with UV light. The composition of the embedding matrix has an important effect on the photostability of the photochromic molecules upon exposure to sunlight, and can therefore be used to design coatings in which the dye molecules have improved durability. In this sense, the incorporation of different amino groups (–PrNH₂, –PrNMe₂ and –PhNH₂) in the ormosil network, results in an enhanced stabilization of the photochromic dye, as compared with unfunctionalized matrices. In matrices modified with aminophenyl groups (–PhNH₂), the photostability of the dye has been increased, reaching a factor of 8, due to the formation of hydrogen bonds between the amino groups and the OH groups of the pore surface, limiting the availability of these groups to undergo side reactions with the dye during irradiation that lead to its degradation. Increasing the photostability of the photochromic dye is an important issue for the long term usage of photochromic materials in outdoors applications, limited, nowadays, by their low durability when exposed to sunlight.

Keywords Photochromic hybrid materials · Photostability · Spirooxazine

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1 Introduction

Photochromic molecules can be applied in a wide range, from optical memory media to coatings for windows, photochromic decorations, optical switches and filters, etc. [1–9]. For all the optical applications, a high photochromic stability is required which is generally obtained by embedding organic dyes in a solid matrix. Among the different photochromic dyes, spirooxazines have been extensively investigated due to their high fatigue resistance [10, 11]. The photochromism of the spirooxazines involves a photoinduced heterolytic cleavage of the C(sp³)–O bond of the oxazine ring that leads to the formation of coloured merocyanine structures, as shown in Fig. 1. The system reverts thermally or by irradiation with visible light to its original colourless form [12].

The photochromic properties of the spirooxazine molecules, such as the absorption spectra upon irradiation with UV light and the kinetics of the bleaching process, have been extensively studied in different solvents [13–16] and embedded in polymeric or ormosil matrices [17–29]. In solid matrices, the photochromic properties of the embedded molecules are strongly influenced by the pore environment where the molecules are located. Moreover, the size and shape of the pores containing the dye molecules have also an important effect on the photochromic properties of the system, as it may provoke steric inhibitions during molecule opening-closing processes [30–32]. The loss of the photochromic properties upon prolonged exposure to UV-light, commonly referred to as fatigue, limits the use of photochromic molecules in outdoors applications or in environments with strong UV radiation. Many researchers had studied the photodegradation of the spirooxazine molecules upon prolonged irradiation with UV light in solution and polymer matrices [33–38]. These

Fig. 1 Colourless and coloured forms of photochromic spirooxazines

molecules undergo degradation in solution and most remarkably in polymer matrices due to the fact that their open merocyanine form react easily with free radicals derived from adventitious radical sources and/or residual polymerization initiators [35].

The aim of this work is to enhance the photostability of a photochromic spirooxazine upon exposure to sunlight by the introduction of amino-functional groups in the embedding matrix. In order to optimize the photostability of these molecules, three different amino functional substituents, $-\text{PrNH}_2$ (aminopropyl), $-\text{PrNMe}_2$ (dimethylaminopropyl) and $-\text{PhNH}_2$ (aminophenyl) were chosen to prepare the functionalized matrices. The composition of the sol-gel hybrid coatings has an important effect on the photostability of the photochromic molecules, and can therefore be used to maximize the durability of the coatings exposed to environmental conditions being of great importance for the usage of photochromic materials in outdoors application.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Tetracetoxysilane (TAS), p-aminophenyl trimethoxysilane ($\text{pNH}_2\text{PhTMOS}$), Phenyl trimethoxysilane (PhTMOS), N,N-dimethylaminopropyl trimethoxysilane ($\text{Me}_2\text{NPrTMOS}$) were purchased from ABCR. Aminopropyl trimethoxysilane (NH_2PrTMOS), propyl trimethoxysilane (PrTMOS) and

tetrahydrofuran (THF) were purchased from Aldrich Chemicals. Ethanol was from Panreac. For all preparations double-distilled water was used. The photochromic dye used for the preparation of samples, 1-propyl-3,3,5,6-tetramethylspiro[indoline-2-3⁰-[quinolino]oxazine] (Fig. 1), was generously donated by PPG Industries, Inc.

2.2 Preparation of films

Samples were prepared from mixtures of TAS, RTMOS, where R is the functional group ($-\text{Ph}$, $-\text{Pr}$, $-\text{PrNH}_2$, $-\text{PrNMe}_2$ and $-\text{PhNH}_2$) and water in a TAS:RTMOS: H_2O molar ratio of 1:1:7. The reaction was self-catalyzed by the slow release of acetic acid from the TAS during hydrolysis. The sols were allowed to hydrolyze for 8 h under stirring at 15 °C. The photochromic molecules were added as a THF solution after the hydrolysis of the sol, to give a photochromic-dye:Si molar ratio of 2:200. THF was chosen as solvent due to the possibility of obtaining highly concentrated solutions of the dye and good miscibility with the coating sol.

A sample volume of 0.1 ml was used for the deposition of the films that was carried out after the addition of the dye using the spin-coating technique (Fig. 2). The films were cured for 24 h at 100 °C.

2.3 Characterization

The darkening of the colourless films was carried out by irradiation with a 365 nm, 100W, B-100AP UV lamp from

Fig. 2 Scheme of the preparation process of the coatings

Fig. 3 Optical setup for photodegradation measurements

UVP. The thickness of the film was measured with a surface roughness measuring system SurfTest SV-3000H4. The absorption spectra of the resulting films as well as the kinetics of the bleaching process were measured using a Varian Cary 50 Bio UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The decay of the photochromic effect was monitored versus time at the wavelength of the maximum absorption of each sample (visible range). This decay or thermal bleaching was recorded at dark at 20 °C. The kinetic constants k_1 and k_2 were calculated from the decay curves using a bi-exponential decay equation: $A(t) = A_0 + A_1 e^{-k_1 t} + A_2 e^{-k_2 t}$. A solar simulator from Oriel, model 96000, with a 150 W Xe lamp and attached with an air mass filter AM1.5G filter (model 81084), was used as irradiation source (sunlight) for the photodegradation of the samples. The power of light irradiation on the sample was 90 W/m². An optical setup was designed to monitor the optical

properties of the photochromic films as a function of the irradiation with sunlight (Fig. 3).

The pore environment polarity in the organic-inorganic hybrid coating was determined by the $E_T(33)$ polarity probe (2,6-dichloro-4-(2,4,6-triphenyl-*N*-pyridino)-phenolate). $E_T(33)$ was used due to its lower pK_a value as compared to $E_T(30)$, 4.78 and 8.64 respectively, allowing its usage on more acidic solutions [39]. The $E_T(33)$ scale is defined equally to that of $E_T(30)$ via equation:

$$E_T(33) = \frac{h\nu_{\max}}{hc} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{\max}} - \frac{1}{\lambda_{\max}^0} \right) + E_T(33)^0$$

where h is Planck's constant, c is the speed of light in the vacuum, NA is Avogadro's number, and ν_{\max} and λ_{\max} are the frequency and the wavelength of the maximum absorption of this dye in the different matrices, respectively. The $E_T(30)$ and $E_T(33)$ scales can be interconverted according to the following equation [40, 41]:

$$E_T(30) = 0.979 E_T(33) - 7.461$$

Fig. 4 Absorption spectra of the spirooxazine molecules in a Me₂NPr-modified silica matrix before and after irradiation with UV light

Fig. 5 Thermal bleaching kinetics of the spirooxazine dye molecules in different organic functionalized ormosil matrices

Table 1 Thickness of the films prepared and spectral position of the absorption band of the spirooxazine molecules in the different coatings

Sample	Unfunctionalized matrix/(HO-Si)	Me ₂ NPr-Si	NH ₂ Pr-Si	NH ₂ Ph-Si	Pr-Si	Ph-Si
Thickness (Lm)	0.300	1.130	1.176	0.725	0.730	0.845
λ_{\max} (nm)	600	614	622	616	613	617

Fig. 6 Kinetic constants of the spirooxazine molecules in different organic functionalized ormosil matrices

3 Result and discussion

The photochromic samples prepared consist of a transparent thin film (thickness & 1 Lm) deposited on a glass slide substrate that acquire a reversible deep blue coloration upon irradiation with UV- light. The composition of the

Fig. 7 Scheme of a pore in a NH₂Ph-functionalized silica matrix where the photochromic molecules are located

Fig. 8 Absorption spectra of the spirooxazine molecules embedded in an unfunctionalized coating (a) and in a NH₂Ph-functionalized coating (b) as a function of the irradiation time with sunlight

Fig. 9 Scheme of the photodegradation process of the spirooxazine photochromic molecules as Malatesta et al. demonstrated in the 90⁰s [33, 34]

films, in which the spirooxazine molecules are embedded, has an important effect on the photochromic properties of these molecules as well as on the photostability upon exposure to sunlight. The photochromic properties and photodegradation of the 1-propyl-3,3,5,6-tetramethylspiro[indoline-2-3⁰-[quinolino]oxazine] upon exposure to sunlight were measured in thin silica films functionalized with different amino groups ($-\text{PrNH}_2$, $-\text{PrNMe}_2$ and $-\text{PhNH}_2$). All samples are initially colourless and acquire a blue colour when are irradiated with UV light, as shown in Fig. 4 for the spirooxazine molecules in a Me_2NPr -modified silica matrix. However, in unfunctionalized matrices, the spirooxazine molecules exhibit a reverse photochromism, due to the higher polarity of the TAS that stabilizes the coloured merocyanine structures [20, 21]. The absorption spectra of the photochromic molecules were measured showing a broad band centred in the 600–623 nm range upon irradiation with UV-light. The position of this band was found to depend on the nature of the organic groups in the matrix (Table 1). The absorption band of the dye molecules embedded in amino modified ormosil matrices shows a significant shift to higher wavelengths, as compared to the absorption band of the molecules in an unfunctionalized matrix. This behaviour is due to the higher polarity of the unfunctionalized matrix ($E_T(30) = 60.2 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) as compared with amino modified matrices having $E_T(30)$ value between 44 and 49 kcal mol^{-1} .

The coloured photochromic films undergo a thermal bleaching at dark upon cessation of the UV irradiation,

recovering their original whiteness. The kinetics of this bleaching process follows a bi-exponential decay in all the samples prepared. Figure 5 shows the kinetic of the thermal bleaching of the spirooxazine molecules embedded in matrices modified with different organic groups ($-\text{Ph}$, $-\text{Pr}$, $-\text{PrNH}_2$, $-\text{PrNMe}_2$ and $-\text{PhNH}_2$). The functionalization of the ormosil matrix with $-\text{PrNH}_2$ and $-\text{PhNH}_2$ groups resulted in an important decrease of the kinetics constants as compared with the $-\text{PrNMe}_2$ functionalized matrix or matrices modified with $-\text{Ph}$ and $-\text{Pr}$ groups (Fig. 6). This can be explained by the interaction of the $-\text{PrNH}_2$ and $-\text{PhNH}_2$ groups via hydrogen bonding with neighbouring amino groups or with residual silanol, as shown in Fig. 7 for a pore in a NH_2Ph -functionalized silica matrix where the photochromic molecules are located. In the presence of water, which allows the transferring of protons from silanols to amino groups, the surface acquires the character of a macroscopic zwitterion [42]. This zwitterionic character of the inner pore surface of the matrix promotes the stabilization of the zwitterionic merocyanine forms of the dye, resulting in a much slower bleaching process as compared with that of the molecules embedded in an ormosil matrix modified with $-\text{PrNMe}_2$ groups. In addition, the shape and the larger size of the $-\text{PrNMe}_2$ groups result in a more effective screening of the OH groups in the pores surface, reducing the polarity of the molecules environment and therefore, increasing the kinetics constants [28, 29]. Another possible explanation for this effect is the formation of micelle like structures in the matrix that are able to

Fig. 10 Photostability of the spirooxazine molecules embedded in organic modified matrices upon exposure to sunlight

accommodate the organic dye [43]. In this case the photochromic molecules are trapped in an environment with much lower polarity.

The flexibility of the functional groups can facilitate the movement of the photochromic molecules inside the pores resulting in faster bleaching kinetics ($k_{(-PhNH_2)}$ [$k_{(-PhNH_2)}$] [31, 32].

Unfortunately, the long term exposure of the photochromic films to UV-light results in a progressive loss of its photochromic properties due to the photodegradation of the dye molecules. In order to study this photodegradation, the absorption spectra of the photochromic films were measured while irradiating with a solar light simulator. Figure 8 shows the absorption spectra of the spirooxazine molecules embedded in unfunctionalized and in

NH₂Ph-functionalized coatings as a function of the irradiation time with sunlight.

The photodegradation of these photochromic molecules results in an irreversible colour change from the deep blue merocyanine to a yellow colour due to the degradation products. In the 90s, Malatesta et al. [33, 34] demonstrated the involvement of oxygen in the photodegradation of spirooxazines as a result of an electron-transfer process from an excited state (most likely a triplet) of the merocyanine to ground-state molecular oxygen, triggering the (irreversible) oxidation process. Figure 9 shows a possible scheme of the photodegradation process of the spirooxazine photochromic molecules as a result of an electron-transfer process from the spirooxazine molecule or its merocyanine form to a suitable electron acceptor [33, 34].

The formation of the different degradation products depend on the acidity of the media in which the photochromic molecules are allocated [33, 34].

The photodegradation process of the spirooxazine dye, as well as the bleaching process, is strongly affected by the nature of the host matrix. The introduction of functional groups into matrices results in an important reduction of the relative amount of silanol groups in the inner pore surface, where the dye molecules are located [31, 32]. This, in turn, has an important effect on the polarity of the matrix and therefore on the photostability of the dye molecules. The incorporation of amino groups ($-\text{PrNH}_2$, $-\text{PrNMe}_2$ and $-\text{PhNH}_2$) in the ormosil network, result in an enhanced stabilization of the photochromic dye, due to the interaction of the amino groups with both, the OH groups on the surface of the pores and the embedded dye molecules (Fig. 7). Figure 10a shows the effect of the different amino groups on the photostability of the spirooxazine molecules as compared with an unfunctionalized matrix. The photostability of the dye has been increased by a factor of 8 in matrices modified with aminophenyl groups (R/Si ratio = 0.5) as compared with unfunctionalized matrices. The interaction of the aminophenyl groups with the OH groups of the pore surface, as well as the effective screening of these groups result in a reduction of the photodegradation of the spirooxazine molecules. In addition, the shape and the large size of these $-\text{PhNH}_2$ groups are probably responsible for the immobilization of the photochromic molecules in the pore, avoiding the rearrangement of these molecules to form the degradation products (Fig. 9). On the other hand, increasing the R/Si molar ratio in the matrix, results in a progressive increase of the durability of the spirooxazine molecules, reaching a factor of 9, as shown in Fig. 10b for aminophenyl modified hybrid matrices.

4 Conclusion

The photostability upon exposure to sunlight of a photochromic spirooxazine derivative (1-propyl-3,3,5,6-tetramethyl-spiro(indoline-2-3⁰-(quinolino)oxazine) embedded in sol-gel hybrid coatings was studied as a function of the nature of the host matrix. The incorporation of amino groups ($-\text{PrNH}_2$, $-\text{PrNMe}_2$ and $-\text{PhNH}_2$) in the ormosil network, result in an enhanced stabilization of the photochromic dye, due to the interaction of the amino groups with the OH groups on the surface of the pores and the embedded dye molecules. In this way, the highest photostability of the dye was achieved in matrices modified with $-\text{PhNH}_2$ groups, showing more than 8 times higher photostability as compared with the dye embedded in unfunctionalized silica thin films. On the other hand,

increasing the amount of the aminophenyl groups in the matrix, resulted in a progressive increase of the durability of the spirooxazine molecules, reaching a factor of 9.

The ability to decrease the photodegradation of the spirooxazine molecules in photochromic materials enhances the possibility of using them in outdoors applications, limited, nowadays, by the low durability of the organic compounds upon exposure to sunlight.

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